

PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT'S ROLE IN THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 6 LEARNERS IN BAYBAY 7 DISTRICT, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive-correlational study investigates the impact of parental involvement on the academic performance of 201 Grade 6 learners in Baybay 7 District, Philippines. Most parent respondents were low-income, high school graduates aged 31–40 working in agriculture, labor, or as homemakers. Despite these economic constraints, students demonstrated high academic achievement (GWA 90–100). The findings reveal a strong positive correlation between home-based parental involvement—particularly homework assistance and creating conducive study environments—and academic success. While parental age, occupation, and income did not significantly affect involvement levels, parental educational attainment emerged as a critical driver of engagement. The study concludes that home-based support is a primary determinant of academic excellence and recommends that schools implement targeted workshops to equip parents from all backgrounds with effective home-learning strategies.

Keywords: *Socio-demographic Profile, Learning at Home, Educational Attainment, Occupation, Academic Performance, Grade 6 Learners, Home-Based Support, Descriptive-Correlational, Philippine Education*

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INTRODUCTION

Parental involvement significantly influences learners' academic achievement. According to Abbas et al. (2023), this concept goes beyond simply showing up at school; it involves a parent's consistent and active participation in their child's learning journey by doing everyday activities such as reading together, helping with homework, and discussing school events play a vital part in boosting a child's educational growth and motivation. When parents are involved in school activities, communicate openly with teachers, and support their child's learning, they not only enhance academic performance but also strengthen the connection between home and school, helping learners appreciate the value of education in their lives.

Research consistently supports the positive impact of parental involvement. For instance, Angwaomaodoko (2023) found that children whose parents assist with homework, attend school events, and communicate with teachers tend to achieve higher grades. Studies by Canter (2024) and Omar (2024) further highlight that collaboration between parents and teachers leads to stronger academic performance and greater student motivation. These are some of the positive impacts that were observed across various countries and educational settings. Similarly to Escol and Alcopra (2024) study, which stated that high levels of parental involvement are linked to better academic outcomes. Meanwhile, Shimi et al. (2024) highlight that such involvement also promotes emotional well-being, positive attitudes toward learning, and enhances social skills of the learner.

In the Philippines, the Department of Education (DepEd) has clearly recognized the important role of parents in a child's learning, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, blended learning was being adopted, since in-person classes were suspended. To support the educational system, the Department of Education in the Philippines implemented learning modalities to continue the learning of our learners. It adopted blended learning, an educational program that combines Modular Distance Learning (MDL) and Online Distance Learning (ODL), primarily guided by DepEd Order No. 13, series of 2020. To support this program, parental or guardian participation is essential, since the parents or guardians are the ones who are at home with the learner. Additionally, DepEd find ways to softly implement this by having a Parent Teachers Association (PTA) webinar, titled "Parents' Role for a Better Learning at Home". It identified the four key parental roles: Facilitator of Learning, Assessor of Child's Self-Directed Learning, Community Mobilizer, and Enabler of Love for Learning (FACE). These efforts guided parents and guardians as they took on a more active role in adopting the different learning modalities.

Based on the PISA 2022 results, the Philippines encountered low scores in reading, mathematics, and science, and one of the possible reasons was the COVID-19 Pandemic- the modalities being used. Possible reasons would be that many of the learners' families cannot afford to buy gadgets, cellphones, or laptops for online learning because some of their parents lost their jobs, some have unstable employment, particularly those working in private companies or working as contract of service, which led to social and economic challenges. According to the study by Arbuliente (2024) further highlights that parents' occupation and educational attainment play a significant role in their level of involvement in the education of their children, which is necessary in buying material for the education of their children. Additionally, a study by Murro et al (2023) found that many of the parents feel unprepared and have a hard time assisting their children in answering the modules, especially for those complex subjects.

After the pandemic, schools gradually returned to face-to-face classes, and the role of parents also shifted. From being hands-on tutors at home, they became more like partners in their children's education, supporting them after school, helping in reviewing lessons, and encouraging good study habits.

Despite ongoing efforts, challenges persist. In the Baybay City Division, particularly in the Baybay 7 District, parents' attendance at important events such as Quarterly Portfolio Day is low; there are only 30% to 50% of parents participating. This is especially concerning for students who are struggling academically, since there are still students who are slow readers and cannot even solve simple numerical problems, and this really affects their learning in school. Learners may miss out on essential support to handle this need. Parents' participation in communicating with the teachers during this program will help them know the strengths and weaknesses of their children in school. This program was for parents to be informed about the performances of their children in school.

However, the results of this study show that parental involvement remains high, even though they did not attend events or activities like this. Their children are still performing well. Maybe parents can continue guiding and supporting their children in other ways that could help them improve and perform well in school.

Thus, this research aims to examine the involvement of parents in the academic performance of Grade 6 learners in Baybay 7 District, focusing on areas such as learning at home, parenting practices, decision-making participation, and familiarity with school communication. By identifying patterns of parental involvement and their role in academic performance. The study seeks to know what parental involvement was being done and most used to improve the performance of their children in school. Additionally, to inform the development of programs and strategies to foster stronger collaboration between parents and educational institutions, ultimately enhancing learners' academic performance.

Research Questions

This research ascertained the impact of parental involvement on the academic performance of Grade 6 learners in Baybay 7 District. It specifically aimed to answer the following key questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of parents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 educational attainment;
 - 1.3 occupation; and
 - 1.4 Household income level?
2. What is the level of academic performance of Grade 6 learners?
3. What is the profile of the involvement of the parents in terms of:
 - 3.1 parenting;
 - 3.2 learning at home;
 - 3.3 decision-making; and
 - 3.4 Familiarity with school information communication?
4. Is there a significant relationship between parental involvement and academic performance?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the socio-demographic profile of parents and parental involvement?
6. What output can be proposed based on the results of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational approach to examine the relationship between various types of parental involvement, including parenting, learning at home, decision-making, and familiarity with school information and communication, and the academic performance of Grade 6 learners in the Baybay 7 District. Additionally, the socio-demographic profile of parents was included to evaluate which factors contribute to improving learners' academic performance. The systematic gathering, analysis, and interpretation of numerical data were conducted using a modified structured survey questionnaire. This approach allows for the identification of patterns and relationships among all variables. As a descriptive-correlational study, it describes parental involvement and socio-demographic characteristics while simultaneously evaluating the relationship between these factors and academic performance. This method does not manipulate any variables, thereby offering valuable insights into their interactions within a real educational context.

The Sample and Locale of the Study

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents

School	Population of Parents	Actual Number of Respondents	
		Male	Female
Sta. Cruz Elementary School	45	0	19
Kilim Elementary School	47	0	43
Gabas Integrated School (Elementary level)	85	0	55
Patag Elementary School	31	0	16
Guadalupe Elementary School	25	0	19
Pangasugan Elementary School	23	0	19
Marcos Elementary School	35	0	30
TOTAL	291	0	201

The respondents in this study included all parents of Grade 6 learners enrolled in schools within the Baybay 7 District. These include: Sta. Cruz Elementary School, Kilim Elementary School, Gabas Integrated School, Patag Elementary School, Guadalupe Elementary School, Pangasugan Elementary School, and Marcos Elementary School, as presented in Table 1. The table shows that there are 291 parents in total, but only 201 responded to the survey questionnaire, and all respondents are girls. The researcher decided to focus on the entire Baybay 7 District since it includes a diverse range of learners, a variety of parent demographics, and different lifestyles. This setting provides an opportunity to explore how parents' involvement, influenced by their diverse backgrounds and parenting styles, impacts their children's education and academic performance in school.

Research Instrument

This study utilized a modified version of the parental involvement questionnaire originally developed by Mejia et al. (2009). This questionnaire also served as a reference and was employed by Tus (2021) in his research. The original version contained 21 items that focused on parents' involvement in their children's education. The researcher modified and adapted the survey to better fit this study's context, adding relevant questions and organizing it into two parts: one on parents' socio-demographic background and another on various aspects of parental involvement, such as decision-making, learning at home, parenting, and familiarity with school information communications. The questionnaire was translated into Cebuano by the researcher and validated by qualified teachers to ensure clarity.

Part I gathered basic information about parents' ages, educational attainment, occupations, household income, and their children's academic performance. Part II contained 29 items assessing parental involvement, with modifications made to improve relevance and clarity; original items were rephrased, removed, or supplemented with new questions. The final instrument had 34 items in total.

To ensure reliability, a pilot test was conducted with 10 parents of fifth-grade students. The initial results showed low internal consistency in the Parenting and Learning at Home sections, prompting revisions. After refining and rephrasing items, a second pilot test yielded a strong overall reliability score (Cronbach's alpha = 0.848), confirming the questionnaire's consistency and suitability for the main study. Validation and some adjustments were made to ensure that the tool accurately measured parental involvement and related factors, thereby supporting valid conclusions in the research.

Gathering of Data

The study began with obtaining approval from relevant authorities, including the Dean of the Graduate School, the Schools Division Superintendent, and the school principals. It also involved sending letters to Grade 6 Advisers to inform them of the study and encourage parent participation. Ethical considerations were prioritized by obtaining informed consent from respondents. Surveys were scheduled for weekends with the help of Grade 6 advisers.

A structured survey was distributed to Grade 6 parents. The respondents will check the boxes to express their level of involvement in their children's education. Once accomplished, questionnaires were collected during the scheduled period at each school. The researcher monitored the collection process to ensure accuracy and timely submission. After collecting all the responses, the researcher entered the data into a statistical software for analysis. Subsequently, the questionnaires were gathered, interpreted, and the results were analyzed in relation to the research objectives.

The study used responses from Part I of the survey to evaluate the socio-demographic profile of parents. Age groups were analyzed to explore their connection to parental involvement, using frequency counts and percentages to identify trends in their involvement based on age.

The analysis focused on how parents' education and occupation influence their involvement in education. Various educational categories and occupations were examined using frequency counts and percentages to assess their influence on academic performance.

The study explored the relationship between household income and parental involvement. Respondents were categorized based on income levels, with frequency counts and percentages used to analyze the data and identify trends.

The academic performance of Grade 6 learners was evaluated using the General Weighted Average (GWA). This average was categorized into five levels: “*Outstanding*”, “*Very Satisfactory*”, “*Satisfactory*”, “*Fairly Satisfactory*”, and “*Did Not Meet Expectations*”. Frequency counts and percentages were used to analyze the impact of parental involvement on learners' performance.

Parental involvement was measured across four key areas: Parenting, learning at home, decision-making, and familiarity with school information and communication. A scale was used to assess involvement levels, ranging from full to low involvement, with frequency and percentage calculations used to categorize participation.

In order to understand the relationship between parents' involvement and the academic performance of learners, the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used. This tool helped assess the relationship between the profile of parental involvement—such as parenting, learning at home, decision-making, and familiarity with school information and the learner's academic performance.

Additionally, to assess the relationship between parents' socio-demographic profile and their level of involvement in their children's education, ANOVA was also employed. This analysis examined the strength and direction of the connection between factors such as parents' age, educational attainment, occupation, and household income level. Specifically, it examined differences in parental involvement and academic performance using the F-statistic. If the p-value is 0.05 or higher, it means there is a significant difference between the groups. The degrees of freedom helped organize the data correctly; the F-statistic indicated whether the observed differences were real or due to chance; and the p-value indicated the level of confidence in these results. Together, these tools provided a comprehensive and easy-to-understand picture of the data.

This analysis aimed to identify trends and correlations between parental involvement and academic performance. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic information and level of parental involvement, while correlational analysis examined the relationship between different forms of parental involvement and students' academic performance. The findings were compiled into a comprehensive report detailing the results of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-Demographic Profile of Respondents

The socio-demographic profile of the respondents, which includes their age, educational attainment, occupation, and household income level, played a crucial role in this study. This information was essential for understanding the respondents' profiles and addressing the research questions. The details regarding their socio-demographic profiles are presented in Table 2.

Age. Many of the respondents were aged 31–40 years old (41.3%), followed by those aged 41–50 years old (32.3%). Only 7.5% belonged to the 21–30 age bracket, while 18.9% were 51 years old and above. These findings suggest that most of the parents were in their economically and socially established years, which may contribute to more consistent and active involvement in their children's education.

Table 2. Socio-demographic profile of parents

Attributes	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
21-30 years (Younger Parents)	15	7.5
31-40 years (More Established Parents)	83	41.3
41-50 years (Parents with Older Children)	65	32.3
51 years and above (Older Parents)	38	18.9
Total	201	100
Educational Attainment		
Elementary Level Non-completer	13	6.5
Elementary Graduate	20	10.0
High School Level Non-completer	42	20.9
High School Graduate	70	34.8
College Level Non-completer	23	11.4
College Graduate	28	13.9
Postgraduate (Master's or Doctoral)	5	2.5
Total	201	100
Occupation		
Farmer	38	18.9
Government Worker	22	10.9
Fisherman	5	2.5
Private Sector Employee	7	3.5
Self-employed	22	10.9
Unemployed	46	22.9
Housewife	21	10.4
Unspecified	20	10.0
Other	20	10.0
Total	201	100
Household Income level (Monthly)		
Rich (At least ₱219,141)	-	-
High Income (₱131,485 to ₱219,140)	-	-
Upper Middle Income (₱76,670 to ₱131,484)	-	-
Middle Class (₱43,829 to ₱76,669)	11	5.5
Lower Middle Income (₱21,195 to ₱43,828)	54	26.9
Low Income (₱10,957 to ₱21,194)	62	30.8
Poor (Below ₱10,957)	74	36.8
Total	201	100

Some studies support the idea that parents within the 31–40 age group are often more active in school-related activities and decision-making processes that would benefit learners' academic performance (Tufail & Zehra, 2023). Meanwhile, parents aged 41–50 may draw from greater parenting experience, although parental involvement may gradually decrease as children become more independent (Yang et al., 2023). Older parents aged 51 and above may encounter generational or health-related challenges, yet they continue to provide guidance and emotional support that positively influence children's educational experiences (Wei, 2022).

Overall, the findings indicate that parental involvement can remain meaningful across all age groups, although the form of support may vary depending on parents' life stages and responsibilities.

Educational Attainment. High school graduates comprised the largest educational group among respondents (34.8%), followed by high school level non-completers (20.9%). College graduates accounted for 13.9%, while only 2.5% had postgraduate degrees.

Many parents had moderate educational backgrounds, potentially affecting their ability to support their children academically. Research by Claudia and Paun (2024), showed that parents with at least secondary education are generally more involved in monitoring academic progress and supporting learning at home. Even parents with limited educational attainment, however, can still positively influence children through encouragement and active participation in school activities (Kantova, 2024).

Although only a small number of respondents held college or postgraduate degrees, these parents may provide stronger academic guidance and educational aspirations for their children. Martinez (2022) emphasized that highly educated parents are more likely to create supportive learning environments and provide educational resources that contribute to student achievement. Nevertheless, excessively high expectations may also create academic pressure and anxiety among children if not balanced with emotional support (Xu et al., 2022).

In general, despite the relatively low educational attainment of many respondents, learners were still able to perform well academically, suggesting that parental encouragement and involvement remain influential regardless of parents' educational background.

Occupation. Unemployed parents represented the largest occupational group (22.9%), followed by farmers (18.9%). Government workers and self-employed parents each accounted for 10.9% of the respondents.

The findings reflect that many families may experience financial instability, which can affect the availability of educational resources and parental support. Nguyen et al. (2020) noted that unemployment may contribute to stress and reduced parental involvement. However, Jensen et al. (2024) argued that parental unemployment does not always produce negative effects on children's school well-being, which suggests that other supportive factors may compensate for economic difficulties.

For farming families, work demands and unstable income may limit direct educational involvement. Nevertheless, Angwaomaodoko (2023) emphasized that emotional, behavioral, and cognitive parental engagement can still improve children’s academic outcomes regardless of occupation. Similarly, government workers and self-employed parents may be better positioned to provide learning materials and attend school activities because of relatively stable employment and income (Mchia et al., 2024; Shah & Hussain, 2021).

Overall, the results suggest that while occupation and economic stability influence parental involvement, commitment, and encouragement from parents remain important factors in supporting children’s education.

Household Income Level. Most respondents belonged to economically disadvantaged groups. Parents categorized as “Poor” comprised 36.8% of the sample, followed by low-income households at 30.8% and lower middle-income households at 26.9%. No respondents belonged to higher-income categories.

These findings indicate that many families face financial limitations that may restrict access to educational materials, tutoring, and other academic resources. Consistent with the Philippine Statistics Authority Region VIII (2024), poverty remains a significant concern among families in Eastern Visayas. Studies also show that students from economically disadvantaged households often experience lower academic achievement due to limited learning support and resources (Idulog et al., 2023).

Despite these economic challenges, the study revealed that many learners still performed well academically. This suggests that parental motivation, emotional support, and effective use of available resources may help lessen the negative effects of poverty on children’s education. Palomares et al. (2024) emphasized that financial stability alone does not guarantee academic success, as parental engagement and support also play significant roles in shaping educational outcomes.

Overall, the findings highlight that while socioeconomic conditions influence educational opportunities, active parental involvement continues to be an important factor in promoting student achievement even among low-income families.

Academic Performance of Grade 6 Learners

This study examines the academic performance of Grade 6 learners in Baybay 7 District during the second quarter of the 2024-2025 school year, specifically analyzing their General Weighted Average (GWA) across various achievement levels. Performance is categorized according to the grading scale reflected on School Form 9 (Learners’ Report Card): 90-100, 85-89, 80-84, 75-79, and below 75, as stipulated in DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015.

The results show that most Grade 6 learners in Baybay 7 District performed satisfactorily or better during the second quarter of the school year 2024–2025. A large number of learners obtained grades ranging from Outstanding to Satisfactory, while only a few fell under the Fairly Satisfactory and Did Not Meet Expectations categories. This generally indicates that the learners are doing well academically.

Table 3. Level of academic performance of Grade 6 learners

GWA	Frequency	Percentage	Academic Performance
90-100	67	33.3	Outstanding
85-89	57	28.4	Very Satisfactory
80-84	57	28.4	Satisfactory
75-79	18	9.0	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 75	2	1.0	Did Not Meet Expectation
Total	201	100	

The learners who achieved Outstanding and Very Satisfactory ratings may have benefited from supportive home environments and active parental involvement. As explained by Shimi (2024), parents who regularly encourage their children, monitor their studies, and communicate with teachers help improve learners' motivation, confidence, and academic performance. In the same way, Utami (2022) pointed out that even simple forms of parental support can positively influence children's academic achievement. These findings suggest that learners perform better when parents remain involved in their education.

Meanwhile, learners who obtained Satisfactory ratings may still need more consistent support at home to improve their academic performance further. Guidance from parents through checking schoolwork, encouraging good study habits, and monitoring progress can help learners become more motivated and focused in their studies. With stronger support and encouragement, these learners may be able to achieve higher academic results.

On the other hand, the few learners who received Fairly Satisfactory ratings or failed to meet expectations may be experiencing limited parental support or other challenges related to their learning environment. According to Chen and Mok (2023), inconsistent parental involvement is often connected to lower academic performance. Similarly, Janius et al. (2024) emphasized that children who receive little support and guidance from parents may struggle both academically and emotionally.

Overall, the findings show that parental involvement remains an important factor in learners' academic success. Learners tend to perform better when parents actively support and encourage them in their studies. Therefore, strengthening the partnership between schools and families may help improve learners' academic performance and overall development.

Profile of Parental Involvement

Parental involvement refers to the active participation of parents in supporting their children's education both at home and in school-related activities. This study examined parental involvement in four key areas: parenting, learning at home, decision-making, and familiarity with school information and communication.

Table 4 shows that parents generally demonstrated high level of involvement across all indicators. Among the four dimensions, learning at home had the highest involvement, followed closely by parenting. Meanwhile, decision-making and familiarity with school information and communication also reflected high levels of participation.

Table 4. Profile of the involvement of Parents

Indicators	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Learning at home	201	92%
Parenting	201	91%
Decision-making	201	80%
Familiarity with school information communication	201	80%
Average		86%

The findings suggest that most parents actively support their children through home-based practices such as monitoring assignments, maintaining discipline, and staying informed about academic progress. These results challenge the common assumption that parental involvement is limited only to attendance in school activities. Instead, the data indicate that parents contribute in many ways, particularly within the home environment.

Overall, the results highlight that parental involvement extends beyond physical presence in school and includes emotional support, guidance, communication, and active participation in children’s learning experiences.

Parenting

Table 4.1. Profile of the involvement of the parents in terms of Parenting (n=201)

Questions	No of Yes Response	Percentage	Description
1. Do you help support your child’s learning by providing nutritious meals and ensuring they get enough sleep?	200	100%	Full Involvement
2. Do you support and reinforce the school’s discipline policies?	195	97%	Full Involvement
3. Have you discussed with your child the value and importance of education?	193	96%	Full Involvement
4. Do you have a designated time and place at home for your child to complete homework?	189	94%	Full Involvement
5. Do you regularly check your child’s homework?	187	93%	Full Involvement
6. Do you monitor your child’s use of a mobile phone?	185	92%	Full Involvement
7. Do you monitor your child’s television viewing habits?	178	89%	Full Involvement
8. Do you ensure that your child maintains good attendance at school?	174	87%	Full Involvement
9. Do you attend any workshops or seminars designed to enhance parenting skills related to education?	142	71%	Moderate Involvement
Average	183	91%	Full Involvement

The results in Table 4.1 indicate that parents showed a very high level of involvement in terms of parenting. Most parents reported supporting their children's basic needs, reinforcing school discipline, discussing the importance of education, and monitoring school-related activities at home.

The strongest area of involvement was providing nutritious meals and ensuring enough sleep for children. This suggests that parents recognize the importance of children's physical well-being in supporting academic performance. According to Roberts et al. (2022), proper nutrition and adequate sleep positively affect learners' concentration, memory, and overall learning ability.

Similarly, parents' support for school discipline policies and regular communication about the value of education reflect a strong partnership between home and school. Li et al. (2020) emphasized that consistent discipline between parents and schools helps improve learners' self-regulation and behavior. In the same way, Şengönül (2022) noted that parent-child discussions about education strengthen students' motivation and academic aspirations.

However, attendance in parenting workshops and seminars received the lowest level of involvement within this category, although it still reflected moderate participation. This may suggest that while parents are highly involved at home, some may have limited time or access to formal parenting programs.

Overall, the findings show that parents are highly committed to supporting their children through positive parenting practices, particularly in creating a supportive home environment that encourages learning and discipline.

Learning at Home

Table 4.2 reveals that parents demonstrated the highest level of involvement in learning at home. Most parents reported holding their children accountable for completing assignments, discussing school lessons, encouraging reading habits, and providing time and space for studying.

These findings suggest that parents play an active role in reinforcing learning outside the classroom. In particular, monitoring assignments and discussing school activities may help children develop responsibility and stronger study habits. According to Owen (2024), parental involvement in homework and academic monitoring is positively associated with improved academic performance.

Moreover, the high percentage of parents who encourage reading highlights the importance they place on literacy development. Research by G. Hernandez and Decena (2024) found that parental involvement in reading activities contributes significantly to children's reading proficiency and academic growth.

Table 4.2 Profile of the involvement of the parents in terms of Learning at Home (n=201)

Questions	No of Yes Response	Percentage	Description
1. Do you hold your child accountable for completing all assignments on time and to the best of their ability?	198	99%	Full Involvement
2. Do you engage in discussions with your child about what they are learning in school?	192	96%	Full Involvement
3. Do you encourage your child to read by discussing what they read and how often they reads?	191	95%	Full Involvement
4. Do you provide a quiet and organized space for your child to study or do homework?	189	94%	Full Involvement
5. Do you set aside specific time for your child to complete homework each day?	180	90%	Full Involvement
6. Are you familiar with the information and skills your child should master at their grade level across subject areas?	154	77%	High Involvement
Average	184	92%	Full Involvement

On the other hand, familiarity with grade-level competencies had the lowest response within this category. This may indicate that some parents are less aware of the specific skills and competencies expected at their children’s grade level. Prabhakar (2024) notes, parental awareness of curriculum standards is closely linked to improved educational support at home.

Overall, the results show that parents are strongly involved in supporting learning at home, there is still a need to strengthen parents’ understanding of grade-level expectations and curriculum standards.

Decision-making

Table 4.3 shows that parents generally demonstrated a high level of involvement in decision-making related to their children’s education. Most parents reported discussing family matters with their children and considering their preferences when making educational decisions.

These findings indicate that parents value open communication and recognize the importance of involving children in matters that affect their education. According to Contreras (2024), supportive family discussions and shared decision-making contribute positively to learners’ academic motivation and confidence.

Likewise, many parents also reported consulting teachers or school staff before making important educational decisions. This reflects a positive home-school relationship and highlights parents’ willingness to collaborate with educators. Maimad et al. (2023) emphasized

that consistent communication between parents and teachers supports better academic outcomes among learners.

Table 4.3. Profile of the involvement of the parents in terms of decision-making (n=201)

Questions	No of Yes Response	Percentage	Description
1. Do you discuss important family decisions with your child to gather their opinions and feelings?	190	95%	Full Involvement
2. When making decisions regarding your child’s education, do you consider their preferences and interests?	187	93%	Full Involvement
3. Do you consult with teachers or school staff before making significant decisions about your child’s education?	171	85%	High Involvement
4. Have you attended at least one meeting of the Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) this year?	170	85%	High Involvement
5. Do you involve your child in decisions that affect their education, such as choosing extracurricular activities?	135	67%	Moderate Involvement
6. Have you provided information to your School Governing Council (SGC) or served as a parent representative on the SGC?	114	57%	Low Involvement
Average	161	80%	High Involvement

However, involvement in formal school governance, such as participation in the School Governing Council (SGC), showed the lowest response in this category. This suggests that although parents are active in supporting their children directly, fewer are involved in institutional or organizational school activities.

Overall, the findings suggest that parents are actively involved in educational decision-making, particularly through communication and collaboration within the family and school environment.

Familiarity with School Information Communication

Table 4.4 indicates that parents generally showed a high level of familiarity with school information and communication. Most parents were aware of their children’s academic strengths and weaknesses and actively supported learning aligned with their children’s future career goals.

The findings imply that parents closely monitor their children’s academic progress and recognize the importance of preparing them for future opportunities. According to Siddiqui et al. (2023), parental awareness of children’s academic performance significantly contributes to better learning outcomes.

Table 4.4 Profile of the involvement of the parents in terms of familiarity with school information communication (n=201)

Questions	No of Yes Response	Percentage	Description
1. Are you aware of your child’s academic strengths and weaknesses?	185	92%	Full Involvement
2. Do you ensure that your child learns lessons/ competencies that prepare them for their chosen career path?	180	90%	Full Involvement
3. Do you proactively contact your child’s teacher or principal to show your support?	169	84%	High Involvement
4. Are you familiar with the grading scale used on your child’s report card?	168	84%	High Involvement
5. Have you attended at least one parent-teacher conference with your child’s teacher(s)?	147	73%	Moderate Involvement
6. Are you familiar with the additional services provided at your child’s school (e.g., speech therapy, resources for gifted learners, counseling)?	121	60%	Moderate Involvement
7. Have you read the school’s student handbook?	102	51%	Low Involvement
8. Do you regularly read the school newsletter/paper?	101	50%	Low Involvement
Average	162	80%	High Involvement

In addition, many parents reported maintaining communication with teachers and school administrators. This reflects parents’ willingness to stay informed and involved in their children’s education. However, lower involvement was observed in reading school newsletters and student handbooks. This may indicate that parents prefer direct communication with teachers over written school materials, or that they experience difficulty accessing formal school information.

Similarly, awareness of additional school services received lower responses, suggesting that some parents may not be fully informed about programs available to support learners. As noted by Lucero (2021), barriers such as limited time and communication challenges may affect parental access to school information.

Overall, the findings show that parents maintain strong communication with schools, although schools may still need to improve information dissemination and make school resources more accessible to families.

Relationship between Parental Involvement and Academic Performance

Table 5. ANOVA results on the differences in parental involvement among academic performance categories

<i>Parental Involvement</i>	<i>Comparison Academic Performance</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>F-computed</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Significance</i>
Parenting	GWA	4	1.457	0.217	Not Significant
Learning at Home	GWA	4	3.282	0.012	Significant
Decision Making	GWA	4	1.805	0.129	Not Significant
Familiarity with School Communication Information	GWA	4	0.799	0.527	Not Significant

Parental involvement plays an important role in shaping students’ academic performance. The findings of this study show that among the different dimensions of parental involvement, *Learning at Home* was the only factor that showed a significant relationship with students’ General Weighted Average (GWA). This suggests that academic support provided within the home environment has a stronger influence on student achievement compared to other forms of parental involvement.

The results indicate that students tend to perform better when parents actively monitor assignments, encourage study habits, and engage in discussions about school-related activities. Home-based involvement appears to create a supportive learning environment that helps students become more responsible and academically motivated. This supports the idea that consistent parental guidance outside the classroom contributes positively to academic success.

The post hoc analysis further highlights that students with higher academic performance demonstrated stronger levels of parental involvement in learning at home than students with average academic performance. This pattern suggests that direct educational support from parents may help strengthen students’ confidence, discipline, and engagement in learning.

On the other hand, *Parenting*, *Decision-Making*, and *Familiarity with School Communication Information* did not show a significant relationship with academic performance. Although these dimensions reflect positive parental engagement, the findings imply that they may influence students in more indirect ways and may not immediately translate into higher academic grades.

Overall, the results emphasize that not all forms of parental involvement affect academic performance in the same way. Among the different dimensions examined, learning

support at home emerged as the most influential factor linked to students' academic achievement.

Relationship between Socio-demographic Profile of Parents and Parental Involvement

Table 6 presents the differences in parental involvement across various socio-demographic factors.

Table 6. ANOVA results on the differences in parental involvement across socio-demographic profiles

Comparison					
<i>Parental Involvement</i>	<i>Socio-Demographic Profile</i>	Df	F-computed	p-value	Significance
Parenting	Age	4	0.233	0.926	Not Significant
	Educational attainment	6	0.568	0.756	Not Significant
	Occupation	8	0.613	0.767	Not Significant
	Household income level	5	0.775	0.569	Not Significant
Learning at Home	Age	4	0.726	0.575	Not Significant
	Educational attainment	6	3.198	0.005	Significant
	Occupation	8	1.309	0.061	Not Significant
	Household income level	5	0.363	0.874	Not Significant
Decision Making	Age	4	0.235	0.919	Not Significant
	Educational attainment	6	0.211	0.973	Not Significant
	Occupation	8	0.505	0.852	Not Significant
	Household income level	5	0.462	0.804	Not Significant
Familiarity with School Communication Information	Age	4	0.194	0.941	Not Significant
	Educational attainment	6	0.327	0.922	Not Significant
	Occupation	8	0.658	0.728	Not Significant
	Household income level	5	0.356	0.878	Not Significant

The findings generally show that age, occupation, and household income level were not significantly associated with parental involvement across the different dimensions examined. This suggests that parental participation in children's education is not solely determined by economic status, type of work, or age, but may also be influenced by personal values, parenting practices, and commitment to children's learning.

Among the socio-demographic variables, educational attainment emerged as the only factor with a significant relationship to *Learning at Home* ($p = 0.005$). This finding indicates that parents with higher educational backgrounds tend to be more involved in supporting academic activities at home. These parents may be more confident in assisting with school tasks, monitoring progress, and creating learning opportunities for their children. Davis-Kean et al. (2021) similarly explained that parents with higher educational attainment are more likely to establish supportive learning environments and engage in activities that enhance children's cognitive and social development.

The post hoc analysis further showed that parents with college or postgraduate education demonstrated significantly stronger involvement in home learning compared to parents with only elementary-level education. The differences became more evident when comparing parents from the lowest and highest educational groups, suggesting that educational background may shape parents' ability and confidence to participate in academic support at home.

On the other hand, comparisons among parents with relatively similar educational levels did not reveal significant differences in involvement. This pattern suggests that parental involvement tends to increase more noticeably when there is a wider gap in educational attainment.

Overall, the findings highlight that educational attainment is an important factor influencing parental involvement in learning at home. While most socio-demographic variables showed limited influence, parents' educational background appeared to strengthen their engagement in supporting their children's academic learning.

CONCLUSION

Summary of Findings

The study established that “Learning at Home” was the only parental involvement dimension significantly associated with learners' academic performance. This finding suggests that direct educational support provided in the home environment has a stronger and more immediate effect on learners' achievement compared to other forms of parental involvement.

One possible explanation is that home-based learning activities directly reinforce classroom instruction. Parents who assist with assignments, discuss lessons, monitor study habits, and encourage reading help strengthen learners' understanding of academic content. These consistent interactions may improve learners' confidence, motivation, discipline, and academic engagement.

In the context of the Baybay 7 District of Baybay City Division, home-based support may also serve as an important compensatory mechanism for limited educational resources. Despite many families belonging to low-income households, learners still achieved satisfactory

to outstanding academic performance. This indicates that meaningful parental support does not necessarily depend on financial capability. Instead, consistent encouragement, monitoring, and emotional support may significantly contribute to educational success.

Interestingly, although parenting practices, decision-making involvement, and familiarity with school communication all reflected high levels of participation, these dimensions did not significantly predict academic performance. This may indicate that while these forms of involvement contribute positively to learners' emotional well-being, social development, and behavior, they may not directly translate into improved academic grades.

The findings also revealed that age, occupation, and household income level did not significantly influence parental involvement. These non-significant findings are important because they suggest that effective parental support can occur regardless of socio-economic background. In this community, the willingness of parents to support learning at home may function as a powerful equalizer that reduces the educational disadvantages commonly associated with poverty.

The study, therefore, emphasizes that academic success is not solely dependent on financial resources or formal school participation. Rather, consistent and intentional home-based learning support appears to be the most critical factor influencing learners' achievement.

Conclusion

The study demonstrated that parental involvement remains an essential factor in learners' academic success, particularly through learning support provided at home. Among all dimensions of parental involvement examined, "Learning at Home" emerged as the only significant predictor of academic performance. This indicates that direct academic assistance, such as monitoring assignments, discussing lessons, encouraging reading, and providing a structured learning environment, plays a critical role in improving learners' achievement.

The findings further revealed that socio-demographic factors such as age, occupation, and household income did not significantly affect parental involvement. This suggests that effective home-based academic support may outweigh traditional socio-economic barriers in influencing learners' performance. Even parents from financially challenged households were able to contribute positively to their children's education through consistent encouragement and guidance.

Although parenting practices, decision-making participation, and familiarity with school communication showed high levels of involvement, these dimensions were not significantly associated with academic performance. This highlights that not all forms of parental involvement influence learners' achievement equally.

Overall, the study emphasizes that meaningful parental engagement does not solely depend on economic resources or formal school participation. Rather, the most powerful

influence comes from sustained and intentional support for learning within the home environment.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are presented as derived from the conclusions and findings of the study:

Learning at Home significantly influenced academic performance.

1. Schools should conduct parent capability-building seminars focused on homework assistance, reading support, study routines, and effective home-learning strategies.

Parents showed high involvement but lacked familiarity with grade-level competencies.

2. Teachers should provide simplified grade-level learning guides, sample activities, and subject competency checklists during parent meetings.

Parents were less involved in formal school governance activities.

3. Schools should organize informal orientation sessions and flexible participation opportunities to encourage greater parent involvement in school governance.

Parents relied more on direct communication than written school materials.

4. Schools should improve communication strategies through multilingual notices, SMS updates, simplified handbooks, and community-based orientations.

Socio-economic status did not significantly limit parental involvement.

5. Schools and local stakeholders should promote low-cost and practical home-learning strategies accessible to all parents, regardless of income level.

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